

What Bitcoin Can't Do!

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

OUTLINE: What makes Bitcoin unique is what it can't do. Let's look at all the things Bitcoin can't do and how these characteristics of the network are what really matter, for the future.

<https://twitter.com/mlrichard/status/872811595419832320>

2. Keywords

Human rights, exchange, freedom, anarchy,

Author biography

Marie-Lynn Richard As a child of the US/CAN Military Industrial Complex, Marie-Lynn Richard grew up to become an anarchist and social engineer. She used the send her FidoNet face book by snail mail years before the general public discovered the web. As an early adopter of early adoption, she likes to tinker with half-baked technologies and concepts. Over the past 25 years she's developed web-based software for B2B and B2C application and countless intranets. Today she works for #infosec as she helps people secure all kinds of digital assets.

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